

Luteinizing Hormone Levels as a Biological Mechanism for Polycystic Ovary Syndrome

Asha Lockett¹, Tiffany Field²

Fielding Graduate University.

ABSTRACT

Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is a pervasive endocrine condition that impacts a vast number of women in their reproductive years. PCOS is manifested by a range of symptoms, including high levels of androgens, abnormal menstrual cycles, and ovarian cysts. While the exact etiology of PCOS remains unclear, recent research has highlighted the role of luteinizing hormone (LH) dysregulation as a key biological mechanism underlying the condition. Elevated LH levels are commonly observed in women with PCOS, disrupting the balance between LH and follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) secretion. This LH imbalance leads to impaired ovarian function, contributing to anovulation, androgen excess, and the formation of cystic follicles. Moreover, elevated LH levels can stimulate excessive androgen production from the theca cells of the ovaries, exacerbating the symptoms of hirsutism and acne. This paper analyzes scholarly research articles and critically reviews LH's physiological role in ovarian function and its dysregulation in PCOS, emphasizing how LH hypersecretion contributes to the syndrome's pathophysiology.

KEYWORDS: Polycystic Ovary Syndrome, PCOS, Luteinizing Hormone

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
19 September

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com>

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Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is one of the most prevalent endocrine disorders impacting females of reproductive age, with an approximate prevalence of 8-13%, with around 70% of women being undiagnosed (World Health Organization [WHO], 2023). PCOS is described as a combination of biochemical and clinical attributes, including a woman's menstrual cycle being irregular, the presence of various cysts in the ovaries, and hyperandrogenism. The exact etiology of PCOS remains unclear, but it is widely understood to comprise complex interactions between genetic, environmental, and hormonal factors (Jabeen et al., 2022; Singh et al., 2023). One of the most significant hormonal abnormalities observed in PCOS cases is the imbalance of luteinizing hormone (LH) and follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) levels, which play vital roles in regulating the ovarian cycle (Singh et al., 2023).

In a typical menstrual cycle, LH and FSH maintain a delicate balance, with FSH promoting follicular growth and LH triggering ovulation. However, in women with PCOS, elevated LH levels, often in the presence of low or normal

FSH levels, disrupt this balance (Fattah et al., 2022). This dysregulation of LH secretion is thought to be a central mechanism in the pathophysiology of PCOS, contributing to both ovarian dysfunction and the clinical features of the disorder, such as anovulation, infertility, and excessive androgen production (Pratama et al., 2024). The excess LH stimulates theca cells in the ovaries to produce elevated levels of androgens (e.g., testosterone), leading to symptoms like hirsutism, acne, and scalp hair thinning (Jabeen et al., 2022; Pratama et al., 2024). Furthermore, the abnormal LH secretion prevents eggs' proper maturation and release, resulting in anovulation and the formation of cystic follicles. This paper discusses the role of LH in regulating ovarian function. It will also explore how dysregulation of LH secretion may serve as a central biological mechanism for the development and progression of PCOS. Understanding the role of LH in this condition is crucial for identifying more effective therapeutic strategies aimed at restoring hormonal balance and alleviating PCOS symptoms.

POLYCYSTIC OVARY SYNDROME

Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS) name comes from the appearance of the ovaries on ultrasound, where numerous

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small cysts (follicles) may be seen due to incomplete follicular maturation and lack of ovulation (Stanczak et al., 2024).

PCOS SYMPTOMS

The clinical features of PCOS can manifest differently for every woman, but the most frequent symptoms will be listed in this section.

The first symptom includes irregular or abnormal menstrual cycles; women struggling with PCOS may have infrequent, absent, or irregular periods (Singh et al., 2023). This occurs due to anovulation (lack of ovulation), which prevents the normal menstrual cycle from occurring. Hyperandrogenism, which involves elevated levels of male hormones (androgens) like testosterone, is common in PCOS, leading to symptoms like hirsutism which is described as excessive hair growth on various parts of the body that is typically seen in men (i.e., face, stomach, chest). Other symptoms, such as acne (i.e., increased breakouts on the back, chest, and face); alopecia (i.e., thinning or loss of hair, particularly on the scalp); polycystic ovaries, which are ovaries that are enlarged and contain many small cysts (immature follicles) that fail to develop into mature eggs are also seen in women with PCOS (Jabeen et al., 2022; WHO, 2023). Women with PCOS often experience difficulty getting pregnant due to a lack of ovulation, which makes it harder to conceive (Stanczak et al., 2024). Additionally, many women who experience PCOS tend to be overweight or obese, which may exacerbate the symptoms of PCOS. Moreover, insulin resistance is common in women with PCOS, which means their bodies (i.e., cells) do not react appropriately to insulin (Singh et al., 2023; Witchel et al., 2019). This can lead to elevated levels of insulin in the blood, contributing to weight gain and increasing the probability of being diagnosed with type 2 diabetes (Bulsara et al., 2021).

CAUSES AND RISK FACTORS

The cause of PCOS has not been discovered as of yet, which has made it difficult to treat. However, the consensus is that PCOS may stem from a combination of one's environment and genetics. Some of the critical risk factors and causes will be discussed in this section.

One of the main risk factors for PCOS is genetics; research has shown that women with PCOS tend to have other family members who also have the syndrome, which suggests that genetics may play a critical role in the etiology of PCOS (Singh et al., 2023). Specific genes related to hormone regulation and metabolic function may predispose women to develop PCOS. Additionally, women with PCOS tend to have hormonal imbalances that are often characterized by elevated levels of luteinizing hormone (LH), male hormones (androgens), and sometimes insulin (Bulsara et al., 2021; Ndefo et al., 2013; Singh et al., 2023). The disparity between LH and follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) is a significant factor that disrupts ovulation. Another risk factor is insulin

resistance. Many women diagnosed with PCOS are insulin-resistant, meaning their bodies require more insulin to process glucose (Witchel et al., 2019). The elevation of insulin in the female body can activate the ovaries to produce higher levels of androgens, leading to symptoms such as acne, hirsutism, and menstrual irregularities (Singh et al., 2023). Lastly, obesity is a risk factor due to excess weight, especially abdominal fat, which can worsen the hormonal imbalance and insulin resistance associated with PCOS, further exacerbating symptoms (Cowan et al., 2023; Singh et al., 2023).

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF PCOS

The underlying mechanism of PCOS involves an imbalance in regulating the hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian axis, which regulates the menstrual cycle (Ndefo et al., 2013). In regular cycles, the gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH) is released from the hypothalamus, stimulating the pituitary to produce LH and FSH (Singh et al., 2023). These hormones, in turn, manage ovarian function. However, in PCOS, there is often an abnormal elevation of LH levels relative to FSH, which leads to deleterious outcomes, such as impaired follicular development (Stanczak et al., 2024). In PCOS, ovary follicles fail to mature correctly and do not ovulate, resulting in anovulation (lack of ovulation) (Singh et al., 2023; Stanczak et al., 2024). This leads to irregular or absent menstrual cycles and infertility. Another outcome of abnormal LH levels is increased androgen production (Bulsara et al., 2021). Heightened LH levels prompt the ovaries to produce more androgens, such as the male hormone testosterone. Moreover, insulin resistance, common in PCOS, increases insulin levels (Cowan et al., 2023). Thus, high insulin can cause elevated androgens from the ovaries, worsen insulin resistance, and increase the risk of metabolic complications.

DIAGNOSIS OF PCOS

The diagnosis of PCOS is dependent on having at least two of the following three criteria, known as the Rotterdam criteria (Witchel et al., 2019; Stanczak et al., 2024):

- 1. Irregular or absent ovulation** (evidenced by irregular menstrual cycles or lack of ovulation (i.e., anovulation).
- 2. Features of hyperandrogenism** (such as excess testosterone or hirsutism).
- 3. Polycystic ovaries** (these cysts can be identified via ultrasound and are typically diagnosed as PCOS when 12 or more cysts are found).

Before PCOS is diagnosed, other causes of similar symptoms are ruled out, such as thyroid disorders or adrenal diseases (Witchel et al., 2019). A thorough evaluation, including blood tests (for hormone levels like LH, FSH, testosterone, and insulin), pelvic ultrasound, and a detailed clinical history, is typically used to diagnose.

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Treatment Options for PCOS

There is no cure for PCOS, but treatment options focus on managing symptoms and preventing complications. The choice of treatment depends on the woman's symptoms and her reproductive goals. One treatment involves diet and exercise (Cowan et al., 2023). Losing weight by dieting and exercising is often recommended, especially for overweight women with PCOS. Even a modest weight loss can help improve symptoms, such as insulin resistance and abnormal menstrual cycles, and aid in reducing symptoms like acne and hirsutism (Cowan et al., 2023). Research has shown that a low glycemic diet, a diet low in refined carbohydrates and sugars, can help manage insulin resistance and improve metabolic health (Cowan et al., 2023).

Another form of treatment is oral contraceptives (OCPs). OCPs are commonly prescribed to help manage one's menstrual cycle, decrease androgens, and improve symptoms related to elevated testosterone, like excess hair growth and acne (Singh et al., 2023). They work by suppressing LH and FSH secretion and preventing ovulation. Medications like spironolactone (i.e., anti-androgens) can block the effects of excess androgens, reducing symptoms like hirsutism and acne (Bulsara et al., 2021).

Metformin, another medicated treatment, is a medication that improves insulin sensitivity, helping to reduce insulin levels and regulate menstrual cycles in women with insulin resistance (Bulsara et al., 2021; Cowan et al., 2023; Ndefo et al., 2013). Other drugs, such as Serophene, are commonly used to help women struggling with PCOS to conceive by inducing ovulation (Ndefo et al., 2013). Lastly, gonadotropins are suitable for women who do not respond to oral medications. Therefore, injectable gonadotropins may be used to stimulate ovulation (Ndefo et al., 2013). For women with PCOS who are infertile due to anovulation, treatments that aid in fertility, such as ovulation induction, in vitro fertilization (IVF), or ovarian drilling (a surgical procedure to reduce androgen levels), may be considered.

Long-Term Health Risks of PCOS

In addition to reproductive issues, PCOS is linked with several chronic health risks, including infertility due to anovulation; PCOS is suggested to be one of the leading causes or risk factors of infertility (Bulsara et al., 2021; Cowan et al., 2023; WHO, 2023; Witchel et al., 2019). Women with PCOS also have an increased risk of being diagnosed with endometrial cancer due to prolonged unopposed estrogen exposure from anovulation. Additionally, PCOS is associated with higher risks of being overweight, diabetes (i.e., type 2), hypertension, and cardiovascular disease, mainly due to insulin resistance (Ajmal et al., 2019; Bulsara et al., 2021). It is also important to note that women with PCOS have higher rates of developing sleep apnea than women without PCOS, especially if they are overweight or obese (Ajmal et al., 2019).

Luteinizing Hormone Levels

Luteinizing hormone (LH) regulates the female and male reproductive systems. It is one of the gonadotropins (Nedresky & Singh, 2022). Combined with FSH, they are manufactured and discharged by the anterior pituitary gland. LH is a vital part of ovulation, reproduction, and hormone production (Wang & Li, 2023). The levels of LH in the body vary throughout the menstrual cycle in women. Understanding the fluctuations and regulation of LH levels is essential for studying PCOS and other reproductive health disorders.

Role of LH

One of the most essential functions of LH is its role in triggering ovulation (Nedresky & Singh, 2022). During the menstrual cycle, LH works in concert with FSH to stimulate the creation of ovary follicles. In women, LH levels fluctuate throughout the menstrual cycle, and the pattern of these fluctuations plays a crucial role in ovulation and fertility (Nedresky & Singh, 2022). During the first half of the menstrual cycle (i.e., follicular phase), LH levels are seemingly low (Kumar & Sait, 2011). FSH's primary duty is to stimulate the maturation and development of the ovarian follicles. In the middle of the menstrual cycle (i.e., LH surge), the levels of LH increase sharply in reaction to rising estrogen levels from the developing follicles (Kumar & Sait, 2011; Nedresky & Singh, 2022). This surge in LH is the trigger for ovulation, when the mature follicle releases an egg. After ovulation (i.e., luteal phase), LH levels remain high to support the corpus luteum, which creates progesterone to maintain the uterine lining (Kumar & Sait, 2011). If pregnancy does not occur, LH levels fall, leading to the disintegration of the corpus luteum and the onset of menstruation. LH also stimulates the ovaries to create estrogen, essential for developing the follicle and regulating the menstrual cycle (Park et al., 2022).

LH Levels and PCOS

In PCOS, a hallmark feature includes elevated LH levels compared to FSH (Pratama et al., 2024). This hormonal imbalance disrupts the normal menstrual cycle and is believed to affect the development of the condition's symptoms significantly. Women with PCOS typically experience higher-than-normal LH levels, particularly relative to FSH (Pratama et al., 2024). Elevated LH levels lead to abnormal patterns of follicular development (Fattah et al., 2022). Instead of one dominant follicle maturing and ovulating, multiple small follicles develop but fail to fully mature and release an egg, leading to anovulation (lack of ovulation). Additionally, elevated levels of LH spark the theca cells (i.e., endocrine cells) in the ovaries to produce increased levels of male hormones, particularly testosterone (Pratama et al., 2024). This androgen excess contributes to symptoms such as an overgrowth of hair in abnormal places, acne, and thinning of the hair on the scalp. Consequently, the increased LH in

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PCOS interferes with the delicate balance between LH and FSH required for proper follicular maturation and ovulation (Pratama et al., 2024). As a result, women with PCOS often experience irregular menstrual cycles, anovulation, and infertility.

Luteinizing hormone is a critical component in regulating reproductive health in women. LH's role in ovulation, follicular development, and hormone production is central to fertility for women in their childbearing years (Bulsara et al., 2021; Pratama et al., 2024). Dysregulation of LH levels, particularly elevated LH in conditions like PCOS, can significantly impact ovarian function, menstrual cycles, and overall fertility (Pratama et al., 2024). Accurate measurement and understanding of LH levels are crucial for diagnosing and managing reproductive health issues, and targeted treatments aimed at correcting LH imbalances can help restore fertility and alleviate symptoms associated with conditions like PCOS.

Critical Review

Limited studies have focused on the causes of PCOS. However, due to the emergence of PCOS cases in the last few years, more research has been aimed at understanding the underlying mechanisms for this syndrome, particularly on the role of LH.

Deswal and colleagues' (2019) study aimed to investigate the association of LH and luteinizing hormone receptor (LHR) gene polymorphisms with susceptibility to PCOS. The primary objectives were determining the frequency of the luteinizing hormone β (rs1056917) variant and the rs61996318 LHR gene variant in women with PCOS. Additionally, the study sought to examine how these polymorphisms might influence the biochemical and clinical description of PCOS, including LH levels in affected women. The study was based on the hypothesis that polymorphisms in the LH and LHR genes could influence the development or increase the risk of PCOS (Deswal et al., 2019). It was suggested that these genetic variations may play a significant role in the syndrome's pathophysiology, impacting factors such as LH secretion, which is known to be dysregulated in PCOS. The research aimed better to understand the genetic underpinnings of this common endocrine disorder, potentially leading to improved diagnostic and therapeutic strategies.

The study involved 300 women, 150 of whom had been diagnosed with PCOS, and 150 were healthy controls. The participants were between 16 and 45 years old, and the Rotterdam criteria were used to diagnose PCOS. The researchers employed polymerase chain reaction-restriction fragment length polymorphism (PCR-RFLP) to analyze the genetic variations in the LH and LHR genes. This technique allows for the detection of specific nucleotide mutations. This method comprehensively analyzed the genetic factors contributing to PCOS susceptibility.

The results of the study revealed that 88% of the women with PCOS had heightened levels of LH. Furthermore, LH levels

showed strong associations with body mass index (BMI), hyperandrogenism, and infertility, which are key clinical features of PCOS. The LH β rs1056917 variant was present in 56% of the women with PCOS and was significantly linked with an elevated risk of developing the disorder. Additionally, the LHR gene variant was found to be significantly associated with PCOS development, suggesting that both genes play crucial roles in the pathogenesis of the condition.

In the discussion, the authors highlighted the importance of understanding the role of LH and LHR gene polymorphisms in the metabolic and hormonal pathways involved in PCOS. The high LH levels observed in women with PCOS, although a known characteristic, have not been sufficiently studied, and further research is warranted. The study also suggested that these genetic variants could serve as molecular markers to detect early risk for women experiencing PCOS. However, the authors acknowledged some limitations, including the study's focus on North Indian women, which may limit how generalizable the findings are to women from other cultural or ethnic backgrounds.

The study conducted by Atoum and colleagues (2022) examined the association between luteinizing hormone (LH) levels and a specific polymorphism in the luteinizing hormone receptor gene (LHCGR), named rs2293275, in women with polycystic ovarian syndrome. The researchers sought to determine how this genetic variation might relate to common symptoms of PCOS, including oligomenorrhea, amenorrhea, hirsutism, acne, infertility, and alterations in LH levels, the LH/FSH ratio, and BMI. The study's findings aimed to provide insight into the genetic factors influencing the clinical manifestation of PCOS.

The study involved 110 women, divided into two groups: 55 women diagnosed with PCOS and 55 healthy controls. All participants were between 17 and 38 years old and were recruited from Al Hikma Modern Hospital in Jordan. The Rotterdam criteria were used to diagnose patients with PCOS. The study measured LH and follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) levels using the Roche Cobas c 502 automated analyzer to assess clinical and hormonal parameters. The genotypic analysis of the LHCGR polymorphism was performed using polymerase chain reaction-restriction fragment length polymorphism (PCR-RFLP) and restriction endonuclease digestion. Additionally, the study classified hirsutism using the Ferriman-Gallwey score; all women with PCOS had a score of eight or more (Atoum et al., 2022). Acne severity was also evaluated using the global acne grading system, in which women with PCOS tended to have a moderate to severe score.

The results of the study indicated several key findings. Women with PCOS had greater BMI values compared to the control group. Ovulatory dysfunction was common, with 90% of women with PCOS experiencing some form of it, including oligomenorrhea in 73% and hirsutism in 80%. Acne was observed in 40% of the women with PCOS, and infertility affected 20% of the PCOS group, a significantly

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higher rate compared to just 4% in the control group. Furthermore, 51% of women with PCOS had LH levels greater than or equal to 10, and 33% had an LH/FSH ratio greater than or equal to 1.5, which is higher than the typical ratio of 1 found in healthy women. The study also found that the GG genotypes of the LHCGR polymorphism were strongly linked to symptoms such as hirsutism, oligomenorrhea, and higher BMI in women with PCOS.

In the discussion, the authors emphasized the significance of high LH levels in diagnosing PCOS, as these levels were essential for identifying the syndrome. They proposed that understanding the genetic polymorphisms of the LHCGR gene could provide a clearer understanding of the pathophysiology of PCOS. Specifically, the rs2293275 polymorphism in the LHCGR gene might serve as a crucial molecular marker for the early detection of women at high risk of being diagnosed with PCOS. The study thus provides valuable insights into the genetic factors that may influence the onset and severity of PCOS.

Despite its valuable findings, the study had some limitations. With the small sample size, it may be hard to generalize the results to other populations. Additionally, all participants were recruited from a single hospital, which further narrows the scope of the findings and may not reflect the broader population of women with PCOS. The study also did not account for potential environmental factors that might influence the development or progression of PCOS, which could be an important aspect to consider in future research.

Another study by Al Kafhage et al. (2023) sought to investigate the serum levels of key hormones, including FS, prolactin, LH, and various hematological parameters in women of their reproductive age diagnosed with PCOS. The primary goal was to explore the association between hormonal imbalances and changes in blood parameters in women suffering from PCOS, with a focus on understanding how these factors may contribute to the condition's development and symptoms. The study's findings were intended to enhance the understanding of PCOS, particularly its hormonal and hematological manifestations.

The study involved 50 women with PCOS, aged between 18 and 46 years, all diagnosed according to the Rotterdam criteria at an obstetrics institution in Karbala. A control group of 20 healthy fertile women with no issues with hormones and no symptoms of PCOS was also included. Several exclusion criteria were applied, such as excluding menopausal women, pregnant or nursing women, those with hyperprolactinemia or thyroid dysfunction, and women with only one PCOS symptom. Data was collected through questionnaires, hormone level assessments, and complete blood count (CBC) tests. Blood samples were drawn after participants fasted overnight, with measurements taken on the second or third day of their menstrual cycle, and a transvaginal or transabdominal ultrasound was performed for all participants. The results of the study uncovered significant hormonal imbalances in women with PCOS compared to the control

group, with increased levels of LH, FSH, prolactin, and thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH). Hematological parameters also differed, with PCOS women showing higher complete blood count values. The study found that women between the ages of 26 and 35 were more at risk for developing PCOS. Additionally, women with a higher BMI were found to be at an increased risk for the condition. Regarding hematological findings, women with PCOS had higher hemoglobin levels and a reduced risk of anemia compared to the control group, along with elevated levels of white blood cells and platelets.

The authors discussed the findings in the context of obesity and hormonal imbalances. They concluded that obesity significantly contributes to the development and manifestation of PCOS, possibly due to the hormonal influence of adipose tissue. The hypersecretion of LH observed in the study was linked to impaired regulation of gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH) and greater pituitary sensitivity. Additionally, the altered patterns of sex steroid production and metabolic dysfunction associated with obesity were suggested as potential causes for changes in LH secretion patterns. The study also highlighted that women in the 26 to 35 age group were particularly vulnerable to PCOS, offering helpful information for risk assessment and preventive measures.

Despite the valuable discoveries provided, there were a few limitations in the study. One of the major criticisms was the relatively small sample size, which could impact the robustness and generalizability of the findings. Additionally, the participants were all selected from a single obstetrics institution, which may limit the applicability of the results to broader populations. These factors suggest that future research with larger and more diverse sample groups would be necessary to confirm the findings and further explore the connection between endocrine activity and hematological values in PCOS.

The study by Lai and colleagues (2020) aimed to investigate the effect of polycystic ovary syndrome on brain activity using resting-state functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI). The study specifically focused on women who were newly diagnosed with PCOS and compared their brain activity to that of women who did not have PCOS. The main objective was to identify functional brain changes associated with PCOS and to examine how these changes might relate to hormone levels in women with the condition. By exploring this relationship, the study sought to provide a deeper understanding of how hormonal dysregulation in PCOS could impact brain functioning.

The study's hypothesis was based on the premise that women with PCOS would exhibit impaired brain activity as a result of the hormonal changes associated with the condition. Specifically, it was expected that the hormonal imbalances seen in PCOS, particularly elevated luteinizing hormone (LH) levels, would affect neural activity and potentially disrupt cognitive functions. The authors aimed to explore how these

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changes in brain activity might manifest in different regions of the brain, particularly those involved in memory and cognitive processes.

The study involved 24 women between the ages of 18 and 45 years, all of whom had been newly diagnosed with PCOS by meeting the Rotterdam criteria. Additionally, 27 healthy women were recruited as controls. To ensure a clear comparison, the control group had no history of diabetes or PCOS in their family. The study employed a cross-sectional observational design. The plasma concentrations of six hormones related to reproduction, including LH and FSH, were measured during the second to fifth days of the participants' menstrual cycles. Resting-state fMRI was conducted for each participant, and brain activity was evaluated using two key measures: the amplitude of low-frequency fluctuation (ALFF) and functional connectivity (FC) analysis.

The results showed significant differences in brain activity between women with PCOS and the control group. Women with PCOS exhibited an increased ALFF value in the left inferior temporal gyrus (ITG.L), suggesting heightened activity in this area. However, decreased ALFF was identified in the left inferior occipital gyrus (IOG.L) and the right superior frontal gyrus (SFG.R). FC analysis revealed a reduction in functional connectivity in the SFG.R with the right middle frontal gyrus (MFG.R). Furthermore, the functional connectivity between SFG.R and MFG.R was negatively correlated with LH levels and the LH/FSH ratio, indicating that higher LH levels were associated with impaired connectivity between these brain regions.

The authors discussed these findings in terms of their implications for cognitive functioning. The altered brain activity in women with PCOS appeared to affect several cognitive functions, particularly visuospatial working memory, face processing, and episodic memory. Specifically, women with PCOS exhibited decreased activity in brain regions related to face processing and visuospatial working memory, while episodic memory was found to be enhanced. The study concluded that the decreased functional connectivity in the right frontal lobe, associated with high LH levels, could reflect impaired prefrontal associative integration. These findings suggest that clinicians should be particularly vigilant in monitoring women with PCOS for potential psychiatric or neurological issues, especially those with elevated LH levels, as hormonal shifts may influence brain function.

Despite the valuable insights provided, the study had several limitations. Clinical data, MRI scans, and hormone levels were only collected once before any treatment was administered, preventing the researchers from making comparisons between pre- and post-treatment brain activity. The authors recommended that future studies employ task-state fMRI to assess real-time brain activity related to cognitive functions such as visuospatial working memory, face processing, and episodic memory. This would help to

further understand how brain activity correlates with practical abilities in women with PCOS.

The strengths of this study include its relatively larger sample size compared to other studies examining brain imaging in women with PCOS. Furthermore, this study was the first to explore the link between functional connectivity in the brain and plasma hormone levels in women with PCOS, providing new insights into the relationship between hormonal changes and brain activity. Another notable strength was that all participants were newly diagnosed with PCOS, allowing the researchers to gather data without the interference of previous hormonal treatments. This provided a clearer view of how PCOS and hormonal dysregulation may directly affect brain functioning.

Another study by Morshed et al. (2021) aimed to investigate the relationship between the luteinizing hormone to follicle-stimulating hormone (LH-FSH) ratio and androgen levels in women with polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS). Specifically, the researchers wanted to explore how changes in the LH-FSH ratio might correlate with hyperandrogenemia, a common feature of PCOS. The study also sought to identify whether hyperandrogenemia is associated with more frequent clinical manifestations of PCOS, such as hirsutism, menstrual irregularities, and obesity.

The study followed a cross-sectional observational design and involved 550 women in their reproductive age between the ages of 13 and 39 years who were diagnosed with PCOS based on the Rotterdam criteria. The participants were recruited by purposive sampling from an endocrinology department. Several clinical measures were taken, including height, weight, blood pressure, waist circumference, and the evaluation of hirsutism using the Ferriman-Gallwey score. Women with a score of 8 or higher were considered to have significant hirsutism. A cut-off value of 80cm indicated obesity, and the hypertension cut-off value was 140/90 mm Hg. An ultrasonogram was also performed to assess ovarian morphology, and participants were instructed to come between the second and fifth days of their menstrual cycle for testing. Blood samples were collected after an overnight fast, and LH, FSH, and total testosterone (TT) levels were measured. An LH-FSH ratio greater than 1.0 was considered altered, and TT levels greater than 46 ng/dL indicated hyperandrogenemia.

The results revealed several key findings: 82.36% of participants exhibited hirsutism, and 70.73% had an altered LH-FSH ratio above the cut-off of 1.0. Furthermore, 43% of participants were found to have hyperandrogenemia. The study identified a positive correlation between serum TT levels and the LH-FSH ratio. Additionally, women with hyperandrogenemia had significantly higher rates of polycystic ovaries, menstrual irregularity, obesity, diabetes, and hirsutism. Notably, younger women were likelier to have altered LH-FSH ratios and higher TT levels than those with

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normal ratios. Interestingly, the study found that body mass index (BMI) was not associated with the LH-FSH ratio.

In the discussion, the authors highlighted that the altered LH-FSH ratio was negatively associated with age and positively associated with serum TT levels. While there was a significant relationship between the LH-FSH ratio and TT levels, the study could not distinguish between normoandrogenemia and hyperandrogenemia using the LH-FSH ratio alone. The authors suggested that the ratio greater than 1.0 was the most effective cut-off for diagnosing PCOS but noted that not all participants adhered to it, which meant it was not universally applicable for diagnosis. Furthermore, the frequency of altered LH-FSH ratios seemed to correlate with the cut-off to determine altered status. The study also found that metabolic features, such as obesity and diabetes, were more strongly correlated with hyperandrogenemia than with the altered LH-FSH ratio.

One of the study's strengths was its large sample size, which provided more reliable and generalizable results compared to studies with smaller sample populations. Additionally, the study identified a significant association between TT levels and the LH-FSH ratio in women with PCOS, particularly among South Asian women, a group known for having more dominant metabolic characteristics. This finding adds valuable insight into this population's hormonal and metabolic profiles. However, the study had limitations that must be considered. The authors acknowledged that they did not use a population-specific reference range for serum TT levels, which could have affected the accuracy of their results. Moreover, the study did not measure sex hormone-binding globulin (SHBG), which would have been useful for calculating the free testosterone index and providing a clearer picture of androgen status.

Additionally, the sample in this study was exclusively from Bangladesh, with participants of South Asian ancestry, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to women from other ethnic or cultural backgrounds. Despite these limitations, the study provides valuable insights into the relationship between the LH-FSH ratio and androgen levels in women with PCOS, and it suggests potential areas for future research.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, luteinizing hormone (LH) plays a critical role in the biological mechanisms underlying polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS). Elevated LH levels, in particular, are a key feature of PCOS and have been shown to disrupt normal ovarian function, contributing to hormonal imbalances that are characteristic of the condition. The altered LH-FSH ratio, often greater than 1.0, is frequently associated with hyperandrogenemia, a hallmark of PCOS that leads to symptoms like hirsutism, acne, and menstrual irregularities (Morshed et al., 2021). Studies have demonstrated that elevated LH levels negatively impact brain activity and cognitive functioning in women with PCOS,

highlighting the complex interactions between reproductive hormones and neurological processes (Lai et al., 2020). While the precise mechanisms remain to be fully understood, it is clear that LH plays an integral role in both the metabolic and clinical manifestations of PCOS. Given its influence on various physiological systems, including ovarian function, hormone regulation, and even brain activity, targeting LH levels may offer potential therapeutic avenues for managing PCOS and improving the quality of life for affected individuals. Further research, especially studies that examine the relationship between LH and other hormones in diverse populations, will be essential in advancing our understanding of the pathophysiology of PCOS and developing more effective treatment strategies.

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